

A DMP in a nutshell

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a structured guideline that describes the comprehensive lifecycle of data, from conception to storage, analysis, and preservation. DMPs help researchers to think through all relevant questions concerning the data their research will generate, and ensure attention remains focused on the long-term accessibility and subsequent reusability of their data assets. DMPs provide a basic description of what kind of data will be produced and collected, and details about what will happen to the data both during a project and after it has been completed. This includes statements about the provenance of data, contextual information surrounding the data collection process, how data are conceptually related to data sets produced by similar studies, the infrastructures used to store and manage data, as well as information regarding the publication, citation, long-term access and, if necessary, destruction of data when the research lifecycle is complete. Humanities and social sciences data are unique in that they often consist of private information contributed by individual study participants, thus various questions regarding data protection, copyright attribution, exploitation rights, and licensing are also addressed in this template.

FAIR data principles

The template is also compliant with the FAIR principles to improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of the data. This implies that research data and contextual tools like software should be stored and made available for use in a suitable repository or archiving system and data should be provided with persistent identifiers. Data must be identifiable, accessible, traceable, interoperable, and whenever possible, available for subsequent use. In compliance with intellectual property rights, and if no third-party rights, legal requirements or property laws prohibit it, research data should be assigned a licence for open use.

Note on the handling of the DMP

Please consider the DMP as a research instrument, helping to structure and plan the research process and define the responsibilities within a joint research project. It can vary in length and detail depending also on the type of data and project-stage. Thus, not all questions might be relevant for you, especially at the beginning of a project. Rather regard the DMP as a dynamic document which can be updated until the end of the project. In order to keep track of different versions, the version number of each DMP should always be included in the administrative section below.

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1. Administrative Data

Provide basic information to help identifying your research project and people involved.

Include: Principal investigator, project sponsor/ grant and number, project title, project coordinator (name, affiliation, email address, phone number, and IDs such as ORCID if available), author of the DMP (name, affiliation, email address, phone number, and IDs such as ORCID if available), start and end date of project, version of DMP, date of first DMP version, date of last update, short data summary, any policies you adhere to. You may add any additional basic information.

Version of DMP	X.X
Project coordinator	Name, affiliation, email address, ID's (e.g. ORCID)
Principal investigator	Name, affiliation, email address, ID's (e.g. ORCID)
Author of DMP	Name, affiliation, email address, ID's (e.g. ORCID)
Data officer and responsible for DMP	Name, affiliation, email address, ID's (e.g. ORCID)
Project title (Acronym)	
Start and end date of project	
Grant number	
Data summary	Please also consider: What is the purpose of the data collection/ generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? To whom might the data be useful ("data utility")?

2. Data Characteristics

Provide information on the data collection/ generation process. Which data will be collected and how will it be collected. This also helps in evaluating which software and hardware will be necessary. This includes the type of data that will be generated, a description of methods and data handling as well as the formats that will be generated.

Include: data provenance and data sources, versioning of data, method of data collection, formats of data, amount of data expected to be collected (gigabytes, terabytes), software/ hardware used for data collection/

processing/ storage, aspects on reuse (format), (personnel) costs for data processing and data storage. Will you re-use any existing data and how? What is the origin of these data?

E.g.: The source of the data is/ The data will be collected by, for example, conducting a survey/ by content coding/ by running a code/... this will result in numeric data/ video / The formats generated will be readable using statistical software/ video players/... . During the data processing stage the program XY will be used, while the publication of the data will be in a .xy format to ensure long-term usability. Etc.

3. Documentation and Metadata

3.1. Metadata standards

Provide information on the metadata standards you will be adhering to (you may include metadata standards used by your chosen repository system). Metadata are a standardized scheme to describe datasets. A unified metadata standard benefits findability and usability. The standard used in social sciences is DDI (Data Documentation Initiative). Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and to allow the metadata to be machine-actionable? In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? What naming conventions do you follow? Also consider documenting the version number of the metadata standard you will be using.

Include: structure of metadata, metadata standards, persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI).

E.g.: The metadata standard XY will be used, as this is the standard followed by the repository which will store the projects' data. Etc.

3.2. Documentation

Provide information on which documents you will prepare (documents, protocols, related records...). The documentation outlines the research process and ensures integrity, understandability and transparency of the data collection process and facilitates correct interpretation (also consider machine readability of the data and documentation). Has the software needed to access the data been sufficiently documented? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Include: methods reports, instruments of data collection (e.g. questionnaire, code), codebook, program code for data processing and data code for analysis and tools/methods of long-term archiving. You may also add informed consent forms, transcripts of an audio file as well as tools and software including the version number.

E.g.: The methods report will outline the data collection and processing activities. The code that was used to gather information online will be supplied. A codebook will provide an overview of the variables. Etc.

3.3. Data quality control

Provide information on the quality assurance measures (protocols) you will implement.

Include: all data quality assurance processes, such as pretests, data entry validation, peer-review of data, repeat samples or measurements, definition of standardized processes and checklists, intercoder reliability measures. Provide information about deletion processes. Make sure to consider additional costs. In the event that research data and records are to be deleted or destroyed, either after expiration of the required archive duration or for legal/ ethical reasons, such action will be carried out only after considering all legal and ethical perspectives. The interests and contractual stipulations of third-party funders and other stakeholders, employees and partner participants in particular, as well as the aspects of confidentiality and security, must be taken into consideration when decisions about retention and destruction are made. Any action taken must be documented and be accessible for possible future audit.

E.g.: To ensure that the output of the data collection process will result in high-quality, valid data that can be replicated and reused, the following measures will be taken... Etc.

4. Data Availability and Storage

4.1. Data release and sharing strategy

Provide information on how and when data will be released and made accessible for sharing (and further reuse).

Include: the repository/archiving system(s) and persistent identifiers you will assign, any restrictions in the data release, sharing and usage options, how data will be shared within the project, how data will be shared outside the project, any restrictions in data sharing and why these restrictions exist, access options (open access, restricted access, no-access, scientific use, educational purposes etc.), license options used to pursue sharing strategy (e.g. Creative Commons, General Public License, GNU), machine-readability of licences, embargo periods, informing potential users about the availability of data, search keywords that optimize possibilities for re-use, data discovery strategies, identification procedure for persons accessing the data, interoperability of data, open software applications used, procedure when data collected is combined with data stemming from other sources to ensure interoperability and future reuse, costs for making data traceable according to FAIR requirements (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable).

E.g.: The data will be stored in repository XY under the xyz license. This allows reuse options for Interested users will be informed of the availability through... . Persons using the data will have to log in... . Within the project, the application xy and the storage system yz will be used. Etc.

4.2. Data storage strategy

Provide information on the processes and strategies in place to ensure safe data storage *during* the research process. Safe data storage also includes physical security of infrastructure.

Include: software, collaborator access, security, backups, collaborative workspaces, transfer of data from the field to storage, costs, etc.

E.g.: While conducting research, the open source application xy will be used along with the collaborative workspace yz. During the collection process, data storage safety is ensured by The costs of these factors Etc.

4.3. Data preservation strategy

Provide information on the processes and strategies in place to ensure safe data storage and access to data *after* the research project is completed. Describe which data will be archived long-term and how this decision will be made.

Include: the duration of the guaranteed storage period, what will happen to data not archived long-term (deleting or erasing data, deletion strategies and protocols), where data will be preserved to ensure permanent access (state the name of the repository), any associated costs (for archiving or while processing data before archiving, including legal and ethical questions and software considerations), which long-term formats will be used (does the repository suggest or prescribe any formats).

E.g.: Data of the archive will be archived at repository xy. Respondents of the survey conducted as part of the data collection process were informed of the fact that their answers will be available for others to use. The repository has suggested long-term file formats, which we will adhere to. Etc.

5. Legal and Ethical Aspects

5.1. Legal Aspects

Provide information on any issues that may arise during data collection, storage, release, sharing and publishing.

Include: considerations on legal or ethical barriers to sharing data, data ownership, planned license for reuse or replication, any restrictions on data reuse or replication and why, for projects with international partners consider different national legislation, who has permission to publish data (copyright, ownership, Intellectual Property Rights, data protection), legal situation concerning copyright, exploitation and individual rights, permission to collect data (informed consent), permission for third-party data used in research, processes in case of breaches, personal information been used in the research and is anonymization, pseudonymization or recoding necessary, additional costs for legal questions.

E.g.: Data collected in this research project is owned by ... represented by Permission to collect data was granted by ... in the following forms: Any personal data will be pseudonymized before allowing others to reuse the data. Etc.

5.2. Ethical Aspects

Provide information on any issues that may arise during data collection, storage, sharing, release and publishing.

Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if relevant provisions are made in the consortium agreement and are in line with the reasons for opting out.

Include: ensuring compliance with informed consent, scientific standards and research integrity, necessity of ethical review board, protecting identity of participants, storage and transfer of sensitive data to permanent storage, how to ensure respondents are not negatively affected by participating in the research project.

E.g.: The information provided by respondents is sensitive information. This will be protected by While processing and analyzing this sensitive data, Etc.